

A New Parameterization of Photoinhibition for Phytoplankton

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Description

Mathematical models of photosynthesis-irradiance (PI) relationships in phytoplankton are used to compute integrated water-column photosynthetic rates and predict primary production. Models typically ignore an important phenomenon observed in most experiments: photosynthetic rate remains constant over a range of irradiances before declining due to photoinhibition. In our recent study [1], we suggested a new approach that enables the light-saturating models to capture the plateau in P-I curve in the presence of photoinhibition. We examined the performance of 16 photoinhibition models on 3641 ¹⁴C PI incubation experiments collected over 50 years (1973 and 2022) by scientists at the Department of Fisheries and Oceans (DFO) Canada from 1304 locations. For further details on the methodology of data collection, please see [1].

Herein, we have provided the optimal values of 16 PI curve models, studied in Ref [1]. The optimal values and statistical analysis are done using piCurve library [2] in R.

Contents of Data Files

Opt_ParVal_of_piModels.csv:

Description: This file contains estimated parameters for each sample for 16 photoinhibition models in .CSV format. Details on the models are given in paper [1].

Size: 15.3 MB

Variables/Columns:

- *Model_piCurve_pkg*: Model ID on piCurve package [2],
- *pi_number*: Sample ID
- Optimal parameters along with their 95% confidence interval,
- Statistical metrics: mean squared error (MSE), R2, adjusted R2, AIC, AICc, BIC

10k-Generated-DataSamples-using-double-tanh_Model.csv:

Description: This file contains 10K sets of parameters randomly drawn from the distribution of the estimated parameters from the PI database (Opt_ParVal_of_piModels.csv) for Amirian-tanh model (Eq. 4 of Ref[1]). It provides the predicted photosynthetic rates corresponding to each set of parameter values over irradiance range from 0 to 1200 Wm⁻², reflecting the maximum irradiance observed across the entire database. For further details on how the prediction data is simulated, please see the paper [1].

Size: 284.5 MB

Variables/Columns:

- Column 1: Sample ID
- Column 2: Photosynthetic Rate (Unit: mg C (mg chl a)⁻¹ h⁻¹)
- Column 3: Irradiance Level (Unit: Watts m⁻²)
- Column 4: Maximum Photosynthetic Rate, P_{max} (Unit: mg C (mg chl a)⁻¹ h⁻¹)
- Column 5: Photosynthesis efficiency at low light, α (Unit: mg C (mg chl a)⁻¹ h⁻¹ Watts⁻¹ m²)
- Column 6: Photoinhibition Rate, β (Unit: mg C (mg chl a)⁻¹ h⁻¹ Watts⁻¹ m²)
- Column 7: Dark Respiration Rate, R (Unit: mg C (mg chl a)⁻¹ h⁻¹)

Opt_ParVal_to_Quantify_PhModels_using_10K_DataSamples.csv:

Description: This file contains additional supplementary data related to quantifying the PI models integrating photoinhibition from a simulation study. For details on how the data is estimated, please see paper [1].

Size: 9.7 MB

Variables/Columns:

- Column 1: Sample ID
- Column 2: Model ID (?piCurve::Model_piCurve)
- Column 3: Theoretical Maximum Photosynthetic Rate, P_s (Unit: mg C (mg chl a)⁻¹ h⁻¹)
- Column 4: Maximum Photosynthetic Rate, P_{max} (Unit: mg C (mg chl a)⁻¹ h⁻¹)

- Column 6: Photosynthesis efficiency at low light, α (Unit: $\text{mg C (mg chl a)}^{-1} \text{ h}^{-1} \text{ Watts}^{-1} \text{ m}^2$)
- Column 7: Photoinhibition Rate, β (Unit: $\text{mg C (mg chl a)}^{-1} \text{ h}^{-1} \text{ Watts}^{-1} \text{ m}^2$)
- Column 8: Dark Respiration Rate, R (Unit: $\text{mg C (mg chl a)}^{-1} \text{ h}^{-1}$)
- Column 9: Estimated standard deviation, StDev (`?piCurve::Fit_piModel`)
- Column 9: Optimization convergence (zero means the model is converged)
- Column 10-11: Statistical metrics: MSE, R2

Citation

This database is based on the following paper. piCurve library is also used for the statistical analysis of it. If you use our P-I database in your work, we kindly request that you cite the referenced publication.

[1] Mohammad M. Amirian, Emmanuel Devred, Zoe V. Finkel, Andrew J. Irwin. “A New Parameterization of Photoinhibition for Phytoplankton,” [arXiv:2412.17923](https://arxiv.org/abs/2412.17923), 2024.

[2] Mohammad M. Amirian, Andrew J. Irwin. “piCurve: An R Package for Modeling Photosynthesis-irradiance Curve,” 2024. R package version 0.2.0.

Contact

For inquiries or collaboration opportunities regarding the dataset, you can reach out to Marine Microbial Macroecology Lab (www.mmab.ca) at Dalhousie University. The dataset is created and processed by Dr. Mohammad M. Amirian (m.amirianmatlob@dal.ca) and Dr. Andrew Irwin (a.irwin@dal.ca).

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